

ORNAMENTAL AQUATIC AND SEMI- AQUATIC PLANTS IN COIMBATORE DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

The present study highlights the ornamental potential of aquatic and semi aquatic plant species collected from Coimbatore District, Tamil Nadu. A total of 67 plant species belonging to 36 families distributed in 56 genera have been documented. From phytodiversity point of view, many aquatic and semi aquatic plants still remain unexplored.

Key words : Aquatic bodies, Macrophytes, Marshy, Ornamental Potential, Coimbatore.

INTRODUCTION

India has large variety of aquatic habitats due to geomorphological, climatic, biotic and cultural diversities. The aquatic plants are the most important component of the aquatic ecosystem. They increase productivity of the aquatic ecosystem and help to maintain ecosystem balance. The importance of aquatic diversity for sustainable life support system is an acceptable fact throughout the world. But these aquatic resources have hardly been given due to attention for scientific studies and thus their potentiality remains still untrapped. Once considered useless and water logged, unproductive and sometimes even as deleterious, aquatic and wetland ecosystems are now looked upon as ecosystem with specific ecological characteristics, functions and values (Mishra and Narain, 2010).

Studies on the aquatic and wetland vascular plants of India were done by Agharkar (1923), Biswas and Calder (1936), Bhadri *et al.* (1962), Subramanyam, 1962; Deb, 1976; Cook (1996)

and others. Macrophytes are common features of an aquatic ecosystem, which plays an important role in maintaining the ecosystem of wetlands (Harsha *et al.*, 2006; Dhote and Dixit, 2007; Jeeva *et al.*, 2007; Rasingam, 2010; Sukumaran *et al.*, 2010; Radha *et al.*, 2010; Rekha *et al.*, 2010). Aquatic plants are unique and constitute very important resources of food, and medicine for the rural population. Most of the present day flowers have come from the wild progenitors, a few of which still exist in their natural habitat.

The importance of the aquatic flora in agriculture and horticulture and as a source of food and ornamental can hardly be emphasized. There are several ornamental plants which grow in aquatic and semi aquatic in nature or partial shade and these may be gainfully established in suitable climatic conditions. The wild ornamental potential plants play an important role in environmental planning of urban and rural areas for abatement of pollution, social and rural forestry, wasteland development, afforestation, and landscaping of outdoor and indoor spaces (Kappor and Sharga, 1993).

The ornamental plants act as an interaction of the people towards them for their unique beauty. They are grown usually for the purpose of beauty, for their fascinating foliage, flowers and their pleasant smell (Swarup, 1998). Natural environment provide a rest from mental fatigue arising from the prolonged or intense use of directed attention, which can lead to errors and lapses (Kaplan, 1973). Ulrich (1984) illustrated evidence for nature's direct relationship to physiological state on short term recovery from stress, in which the reports to effects of a natural view on the emotional state and physical recovery of gall bladder patients.

Recent attention has been given on species diversities as measure of pollution or eutrophication based on the principle that in clean water; community diversity is high, while in polluted water the diversity is low (Wilhm, 1967; Wilhm and Dorris, 1968). Nature has given a wealth of wild flower and ornamental plants, unfortunately many of them have been destroyed to such an extent that several have become extinct and survival of many is endangered by over exploitation by human beings (Arora, 1993). Due to rapid pace of urbanization, formation of new human settlements and industrialization these aquatic habitat are in severe threat of extinction. It is therefore an urgent and utmost need to record and to assess the diversity and potentiality of these aquatic plant communities of the district before they will vanish forever.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area:

Coimbatore district is situated in the state of Tamil Nadu in Southern India. It lies between 10' and 12-00' OF Northern latitude and 76-40' and of 8-00' of Eastern longitude. It is bordered by the Nilgiris in the North, Erode district in East, Dindigul district in the South and Kerala in the West. The average rainfall received in Coimbatore district is 670-699 mm for the past twenty years out of the total rainfall 25 percent is received during South West monsoon 49 percent during Oct-Nov. and remaining 20 percent during Mar-May. April is the hottest month

which means daily maximum temperature of 38.2° C and minimum of 25.6° C. The maximum temperature may go up to 41° C on some days. The maximum and minimum temperature is 41.5° C and 16° C respectively. The present investigation was taken up to assess the diversity of ornamental plants which are occurring in the aquatic and semi-aquatic habitats of Coimbatore district of Tamil Nadu (Figure-1).

Figure-1: Study area map of India with Tamil Nadu and Coimbatore district.

An extensive field survey was made to explore the diversity of aquatic and semi-aquatic potential ornamental plants from Coimbatore district, Tamil Nadu during a period from September 2013 to February 2014. During field survey, the plants have been collected in their flowering and fruiting stages as far as possible from the natural habitats. They were identified with the help of local floras, taxonomic revisions and monographs by using identification keys (Gamble and Fischer 1915-1936; Matthew 1983; Henry *et al.*, 1983-1989; Chandrabose and Nair 1988; Subramanyam, 1962; Cook, 1996). These specimens were poisoned, pressed and herbarium specimens prepared according to the standard instructions given by Jain and Rao (1976). The collected plant species were cross checked for correct identification at the madras Herbarium (MH) of Botanical Survey of India

(BSI), Southern Circle, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu. The voucher specimens were deposited in the Herbarium of Department of Botany (BUH), Bharathiar University, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu.

Present study indicates that the aquatic and semi-aquatic wild ornamental potential plants were collected from Coimbatore district, Tamil Nadu is the very important factor for the contribution of biodiversity of existing area. A total of 66 angiosperm plant species of 55 genera belonging

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table-1: List of ornamental potential plants from Coimbatore district.

S. No	Scientific Name	Family	Habit	Habit-at	Flowering & Fruiting	Ornamental Potential
1.	<i>Adiantum raddianum</i> C. Presl.	Adiantaceae	Herb	WL	-	An alluring radiating / evergreen lamina
2.	<i>Adiantum incisum</i> Forssk. (Mytekondai)	Adiantaceae	Herb	WL	-	Pleasing habit with incisum lamina
3.	<i>Aeschynomene aspera</i> L. (Attuneddi)	Fabaceae	Herb	EA	Jul.-Nov.	An enchanting yellow flowers
4.	<i>Alternanthera philoxeroides</i> (Mart.) Griseb. (Kabo-napi)	Amaranthaceae	Herb	EA	Nov.-Mar.	Pleasant crimson colour leaves with small white papery flowers.
5.	<i>Argyrea pilosa</i> Arn.	Convolvulaceae	Climber	WL	Jul.-Sep.	A beautiful prominent bracteate cymose heads with rose / purple flower
6.	<i>Asclepias curassavica</i> L. (Kakkathondi)	Asclepiadaceae	Herb	EA	Feb.-Nov.	Bright cup and saucer shaped orange-red / yellow flowers
7.	<i>Bacopa monnieri</i> (L.) Pennell. (Neerbrahmi)	Scrophulariaceae	Herb	WL	Throughout the year	Charming succulent habit with attractive blue / violet flowers and forming dense mat
8.	<i>Blumea mollis</i> (D. Don) Merr.	Asteraceae	Herb	EA	Jan.-Apr.	Dazzling rose to pink flowers in dense corymbose heads
9.	<i>Boerhavia chinensis</i> (L.) Asch. & Schweinf. (Chattichattaranai)	Nyctaginaceae	Herb	WL	May.-Sep.	An attractive pink flower

S. No	Scientific Name	Family	Habit	Habit-at	Flowering & Fruiting	Ornamental Potential
10	<i>Cassia pumila</i> Lam.	Caesalpinaceae	Herb	WL	Throughout the year	Pleasing prostrate nature of habit with yellow flower
11	<i>Celosia argentea</i> L. (Pannai-keerai)	Amaranthaceae	Herb	WL	Aug.-Dec.	Appealing habit with pink turning white flower
12	<i>Centella asiatica</i> (L.) Urban (Vallarai)	Apiaceae	Herb	WL	Throughout the year	Enchanting habit
13	<i>Centrosema pubescens</i> Benth	Fabaceae	Climber	WL	Sep.-Jan.	Attractive climber with pale violet flowers in racemes.
14	<i>Ceraptoteris thalicterooides</i> (L.) Ad. Brogn.	Pteridaceae	Herb	WL	-	Charming succulent habit with pale green fronds
15	<i>Crotalaria pallida</i> Aiton	Fabaceae	Shrub	WL	Throughout the year	A conspicuous yellow flower in racemes with oblong pod and much exceeding calyx
16	<i>Cyanotis axillaris</i> (L.) D. Don ex Sweet	Commelinaceae	Herb	WL	Aug.-Dec.	Delightful blue flowers in scorpioid cymes with prominent bracts
17	<i>Cyanotis cristata</i> (L.) D. (Neer-pulli)	Commelinaceae	Herb	WL	Nov.-Jan.	Charming habit with Rose-purple flowers in deeply talents having recurved cymes
18	<i>Diplazium esculentum</i> (Retz.) Sw.	Athyriaceae	Herb	WL	-	Good looking lamina
19	<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> (L.) L. (Karishalanganni)	Asteraceae	Herb	WL	Dec.-May.	Alluring white colour flower in capitata inflorescence
20	<i>Eichhornia crassipes</i> (Mart.) Solms-Laub. (Akasa-thamarai)	Pontederiaceae	Herb	FF	Jan.-Apr.	Stoloniferous herb with fibrous elongated roots having attractive lavender to pink flowers in terminal spikes

S. No	Scientific Name	Family	Habit	Habit-at	Flowering & Fruiting	Ornamental Potential
21.	<i>Emilia sonchifolia</i> (L.) DC. (Pooshathalai)	Asteraceae	Herb	WL	Dec. – Apr.	Pleasing habit with attractive corolla in terminal corymb
22.	<i>Glinus lotoides</i> L.	Aizoaceae	Herb	WL	Jan.-Mar.	Charming prostrate habit with leaves cluster at a node
23.	<i>Gloriosa superba</i> L.	Liliaceae	Climber	WL	Throughout the year	Beautiful climber with whorled oblong-long leaves with flat tendrilled apex with stunning red flower
24.	<i>Grangea maderaspatana</i> (L.) Poir. (Masipatri)	Asteraceae	Herb	WL	Dec.-Apr.	An attractive prostrate herb with pinnatifid leaves and having yellow flowers in globose capitulum
25.	<i>Heliotropium curassavicum</i> L.	Boraginaceae	Herb	EA	Jan.-Apr.	Good-looking prostrate succulent herbs with 1-sided spike
26.	<i>Heliotropium indicum</i> L. (Thel-kodukku)	Boraginaceae	Herb	WL	Throughout the year	Charming inflorescence with attractive white to bluish flower
27.	<i>Hydrolea zeylanica</i> (L.) Vahl	Hydrophyllaceae	Herb	EA	Dec.-May.	A spreading sub-succulent herb with gorgeous deep blue petals
28.	<i>Hygrophila auriculata</i> (Schum.) Heine (Neer-mullu)	Acanthaceae	Shrub	WL	Throughout the year	A gorgeous armed reddish subshrubby with strigose-hispid and purple flowers in axillary whorls
29.	<i>Ilysanthes rotundifolia</i> (L.) Benth	Linderniaceae	Herb	WL	-	Beautiful creeping habit with white or pale mauve flowers
30.	<i>Ipomoea aquatica</i> Forssk. (Vellai-keerai)	Convolvulaceae	Herb	FSA	Nov.-Feb.	Pleasing prostrate nature of habit with pink flowers
31.	<i>Ipomoea carnea</i> Jacq.	Convolvulaceae	Shrub	WL	Throughout the year	Fascinating pink to rose flower in panicle inflorescence

S. No	Scientific Name	Family	Habit	Habit-at	Flowering & Fruiting	Ornamental Potential
32	<i>Ipomoea hederifolia</i> L.	Convolvulaceae	Twining climber	WL	Sep.-Dec.	A well branched vine with broadly ovate-cordiform leaves having stunning red flowers
33	<i>Ipomoea staphylina</i> Roem. & Schultes. (Oonankodi)	Convolvulaceae	Woody climber	WL	Sep. – Feb.	Enchanting climbing habit with delightful pink flowers
34	<i>Justicia betonica</i> L. (Vellimungil)	Acanthaceae	Shrub	WL	Throughout the year	Flowers in attractive cylindric spike pinkish white with purple streaks
35	<i>Justicia simplex</i> D. Don	Acanthaceae	Herb	WL	Throughout the year	Charismatic pink flowers
36	<i>Lindenbergia indica</i> (L.) Kuntze	Scrophulariaceae	Herb	WL	Oct.-Apr.	A spreading slender herb with beautiful yellow flower
37	<i>Lindernia anagallis</i> (Burm. f.) Pennell	Scrophulariaceae	Herb	WL	Throughout the year	A gorgeous slender herb with alluring violetish flowers
38	<i>Lindernia antipoda</i> (L.) Alston	Scrophulariaceae	Herb	WL	Nov.-Feb.	Fascinating habit with good-looking blue flowers
39	<i>Ludwigia octovalvis</i> (Jacq.) Raven (Kattukirambu)	Onagraceae	Herb	EA	Throughout the year	A floating herb with aerophore having delightful yellow flowers
40	<i>Ludwigia perennis</i> L.	Onagraceae	Herb	EA	Throughout the year	Good looking yellow flowers
41	<i>Ludwigia peruviana</i> (L.) H. Hara	Onagraceae	Villous shrub	EA	Sep.-Dec.	A robust and compact hirsute subshrub. Flowers with alluring golden yellow petals
42	<i>Melochia corchorifolia</i> L.	Sterculiaceae	Shrub	WL	Sep.-Dec.	A subshrub with obscurely 3-lobed leaves with stunning pink flowers
43	<i>Merremia dissecta</i> (Jacq.) Hall. f.	Convolvulaceae	Twining climber	WL	Nov.-Feb.	Lovely prostrate habit with white-pink flower

S. No	Scientific Name	Family	Habit	Habit-at	Flowering & Fruiting	Ornamental Potential
44	<i>Merremia quinquefolia</i> (L.) Hallier f.	Convolvulaceae	Climber	WL	Oct.-Jan.	A lovely vine with 3-5 fid compound leaves
45	<i>Mikania micrantha</i> Kunth	Asteraceae	Climber	WL	Aug.-Jan.	Florets white to greenish white
46	<i>Monochoria vignalis</i> (Burm. f.) Presl, Reliq. (Neerthamarai)	Pontederiaceae	Herb	EA	Nov.-Mar.	Attractive succulent herb with deep blue flowers
47	<i>Muntingia calabura</i> L.	Elaeocarpaceae	Tree	WL	Throughout the year	Pretty habit with white flowers
48	<i>Nelumbo nucifera</i> Gaertner	Nymphaeaceae	Herb	FLA	Throughout the year	Good looking succulent habit with pink flowers
49	<i>Nymphaea pubescens</i> Willd (Alli)	Nymphaeaceae	Herb	FLA	Throughout the year	Beautiful white flower with succulent habit
50	<i>Opuntia stricta</i> (Ker Gawl.) Haw. (Sappathikali)	Cactaceae	Shrub	WL	Throughout the year	Stunning yellow flowers
51	<i>Ottelia alismoides</i> (L.) Pers.	Hydrocharitaceae	Herb	SA	Oct.-Mar.	Gorgeous white with yellow spotted flowers
52	<i>Oxalis corniculata</i> L. (Pulivayilai)	Oxalidaceae	Herb	WL	Throughout the year	Charming prostrate habit having yellow flowers
53	<i>Oxystelma esculentum</i> (L. f.) R. Br. Ex Schultes (Oosippalai)	Asclepiadaceae	Straggler	WL	Sep.-Feb.	Beautiful purplish-pink with straggling habit
54	<i>Pergularia daemia</i> (Forsskal) Chiov. (Verlipparuthi)	Asclepiadaceae	Straggler	WL	Jul.-Jan.	Delightful green flower
55	<i>Phyla nodiflora</i> (L.) Greene (Poduku-thalai)	Verbenaceae	Herb	WL	Throughout the year	A prostrate herb forming compact mats having charismatic purplish white flower
56	<i>Physalis minima</i> L. (Thakkali)	Solanaceae	Herb	WL	Throughout the year	Enchanting habit with pale yellow flowers
57	<i>Pistia stratoites</i> L.	Araceae	Herb	FF	Throughout the year	A free floating stoloniferous herb sessile leaves and dazzling cream flowers in spathe

S. No	Scientific Name	Family	Habit	Habit-at	Flowering & Fruiting	Ornamental Potential
58	<i>Persicaria glabra</i> (Willd.) M. Gomez (Actalaree)	Polygonaceae	Herb	WL	Throughout the year	A stout dense clumps with good looking rose perianth
59	<i>Polygonum pubescens</i> Blume	Polygonaceae	Herb	WL	Aug.-Oct.	Pleasant habit with charming inflorescence
60	<i>Sagittaria latifolia</i> Willd.	Alismataceae	Herb	EA	Jul.-Sep.	An erect herb with cordate or sagittate leaves with alluring white flowers in paniced or spicate whorls
61	<i>Spilanthes calva</i> DC. (Karisalai)	Asteraceae	Herb	WL	Oct. – Nov.	An ascending scabrid herb with enchanting yellow florets in solitary terminal capitulum
62	<i>Tephrosia pumila</i> (Lam.) Pres.	Fabaceae	Herb	WL	Nov.-Feb.	Good looking white flowers in pseudo racemes
63	<i>Thunbergia fragrans</i> Roxb.	Acanthaceae	Climber	WL	Throughout the year	Fascinating white flowers
64	<i>Urena lobata</i> L.(Ottatti)	Malvaceae	Shrub	WL	Throughout the year	Appealing rose flowers in stout racemes. Flowers evanescent, opening at day-break and fading by mid-morning
65	<i>Urticularia aurea</i> Lour.	Lentibulariaceae	Herb	SH	Dec.-Feb.	A slender herb with large green bladders, turning black with age having attractive yellow flower
66	<i>Vigna trilobata</i> (L.) Verdc. (Pani-payir)	Fabaceae	Herb	WL	Nov.-Apr.	Beautiful prostrate habit with 3-foliolate leaves and its flowers yellow in sub umbellate cluster

Notes: **WL:** Wetland hydrophytes; **EA:** Emergent amphibious hydrophytes; **FF:** Free floating hydrophytes; **FLA:** Floating leaf anchored hydrophytes; **FSA:** Floating shoot anchored hydrophytes; **SA:** Submerged anchored hydrophytes; **SH:** Suspended hydrophytes.

of biodiversity of existing area. A total of 66 angiosperm plant species of 55 genera belonging to 35 families were recorded during the investigation (Table-1, Plates 1-4). The most

represented families with higher number of species include Convolvulaceae (7 species), Asteraceae (6 species), Fabaceae (5 species) and Acanthaceae (4 species).

The family Convolvulaceae was dominated and shows high impact of flora in this region. 24 families were dicots and 6 families were monocot plants indicating that dicots predominate over monocots with respect to species, genera and families. monocots in aquatic habitats have been emphasized by a number of workers (Burlakoti and Karmacharya, 2004; Manhas *et al.*, 2009; Saini *et al.*, 2010;

Niroula and Singh, 2010). Based on the habit of this ornamental species it was identified that the 48 species belongs to herb, followed by 6 shrubs, 9 climbers, 2 stragglers and 1 tree (Fig.2). Among these, Wetland plants were dominated in case of habitat distribution having 48 species, followed by Emergent amphibious hydrophytes (11), free floating (2), floating leaf anchored hydrophytes (2), floating shoot anchored

PLATE-1: 1. *Adiantum raddianum* C. Presl., 2. *Adiantum incisum* Forssk., 3. *Aeschynomene aspera* L., 4. *Alternanthera philoxeroides* (Mart.) Griseb., 5. *Argyreia pilosa* Arn., 6. *Asclepias curassavica* L., 7. *Bacopa monnieri* (L.) Pennell., 8. *Blumea mollis* (D. Don) Merr., 9. *Boerhavia chinensis* (L.) Asch. & Schweinf., 10. *Cassia pumila* Lam., 11. *Celosia argentea* L., 12. *Centella asiatica* (L.) Urban, 13. *Centrosema pubescens* Benth, 14. *Ceraptoteris thalictroides* (L.) Ad. Brogn., 15. *Crotalaria pallida* Aiton, 16. *Cyanotis axillaris* (L.) D. Don ex Sweet

hydrophytes (1), submerged anchored hydrophytes (1) and suspended hydrophytes category occupies one species each (Fig.3).

Dominance of such dicots over the monocots in aquatic habitats have been emphasized by a number of workers (Burlakoti and Karmacharya, 2004; Manhas *et al.*, 2009; Saini *et al.*, 2010;

Niroula and Singh, 2010). Based on the habit of this ornamental species it was identified that the 48 species belongs to herb, followed by 6 shrubs, 9 climbers, 2 stragglers and 1 tree (Fig.2). Among these, Wetland plants were dominated in case of habitat distribution having 48 species, followed by Emergent amphibious hydrophytes (11), free floating (2), floating leaf anchored

PLATE-2: *Cyanotis cristata* (L.) D. , 2. *Diplazium esculentum* (Retz.) Sw., 3. *Eclipta prostrata* (L.) L., 4. *Eichhornia crassipes* (Mart.) Solms-Laub., 5. *Emilia sonchifolia* (L.) DC., 6. *Glinus lotoides* L., 7. *Gloriosa superba* L., 8. *Grangea maderaspatana* (L.) Poir., 9. *Heliotropium curassavicum* L., 10. *Heliotropium indicum* L., 11. *Hydrolea zeylanica* (L.) Vahl, 12. *Hygrophila auriculata* (Schum.) Heine, 13. *Illysanthes rotundifolia* (L.) Benth, 14. *Ipomoea aquatica* Forssk., 15. *Ipomoea carnea* Jacq., 16. *Merremia dissecta* (Jacq.) Hall. f.

hydrophytes (2), floating shoot anchored hydrophytes (1), submerged anchored hydrophytes (1) and suspended hydrophytes category occupies one species each (Fig.3).

The low frequency of aquatic species may be the result of fishing practices. The fishermen choke and net the stream along the banks, where the water was shallow.

PLATE-3:

1. *Ipomoea hederifolia* L., 2. *Ipomoea staphylina* Roem. & Schultes., 3. *Justicia betonica* L., 4. *Justicia simplex* D. Don, 5. *Lindenbergia indica* (L.) Kuntze, 6. *Lindernia anagallis* (Burm. f.) Pennell, 7. *Lindernia antipoda* (L.) Alston, 8. *Ludwigia octovalvis* (Jacq.) Raven, 9. *Ludwigia perennis* L., 10. *Ludwigia peruviana* (L.) H. Hara, 11. *Melochia corchorifolia* L., 12. *Meremina quinquefolia* (L.) Hallier f., 13. *Mikania micrantha* Kunth, 14. *Monochoria vaginalis* (Burm. f.) Presl, Reliq., 15. *Muntingia calabura* L., 16. *Nelumbo nucifera* Gaertner

Plate-4: *Nymphaea pubescens* Willd, 2. *Opuntia stricta* (Ker-Gawl.) Haw., 3. *Ottelia alismoides* (L.) P
 4. *Oxalis corniculata* L., 5. *Oxystelma esculentum* (L. f.) R. Br. Ex Schultes, 6. *Pergularia dae*
 (Forsskal) Chiov., 7. *Phyla nodiflora* (L.) Greene, 8. *Physalis minima* L., 9. *Pistia stratiotes* L.,
Persicaria glabra (Willd.) M. Gomez, 11. *Polygonum pubescens* Blume, 12. *Sagittaria latifolia* W
 13. *Spilanthes calva* DC., 14. *Tephrosia pumila* (Lam.) Pres., 15. *Thunbergia fragrans* Roxb., 16. *Ur
 lobata* L.

They use large fishing nets and eradicate most of the aquatic plants from the main flow of stream. All water loving species were present in few localities with large masses, which help in maintaining the diversity of flora in the stream.

The lack of suitable management and unsustainable utilization of wild resources may lead it to become rare and endangered.

Figure-2: Number of aquatic ornamental plants enumerated based on its habit

Figure-3: Habitat wise distribution of plant species in the study area

Abdullah *et al.* (2009) also mentioned climatic factors as a reason that influenced the distribution of species in certain habitats. The main threat to aquatic ecosystem arises from the cultivation of surrounding land in addition to the lack of knowledge regarding the importance of aquatic ecosystems among the local population. Detailed knowledge concerning the floristic composition, ecology and environmental factor that influence vegetation types, provide a strong basis to research and helps in the improvement of conservation and management practices in relation to the vegetation and biodiversity of aquatic ecosystems.

Wild ornamental species are also the sources for the medicinal significance (Asati and Yadav, 2010). It is very easy for the propagation of wild species by traditional propagation methods. Plants exercise a strong, positive influence on human behavior (Kaplan and Kaplan, 1989;

Harris 1992; Lohr and Relf, 1993). The cost of domestication and maintenance of wild ornamental species is also very less in comparison. It is concluded that the quantitative and qualitative floristic survey, constant monitoring and protection of aquatic and semi-aquatic bodies are the need of the hour in order to save the aquatic flora and to maintain the wild progenitors of the ornamental plants.

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